

SEMANTIC SHIFTING WITHIN THE INTERACTION SEQUENCE

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ABSTRACT

This study integrates the grammar of narrative proposed by structuralist Tzvetan Todorov with the interaction protocol proposed by Krippendoff, and examines the semantic shifting in the context of human-product interaction sequences. First, eighty five metaphoric products were collected and carefully classified into six simplest modes of an interaction sequence based on our integration proposal, which sufficiently explains basic semantic shifting. Second, seven lamps belonging to different modes respectively were chosen as stimuli, and each sequence was illustrated by five frames. The experiment was carried out by forty-eight participants to examine the emotional effects of these lamps at each step. Finally, the early results showed that semantic shifting could influence to the level of emotion at each step, in particular which caused by an atypical form and operation. The special operation could play the role of hook in the sequence to make products more special.

Keywords: motion semantics, interaction sequence, emotion.

INTRODUCTION

Researchers have gradually focused on the relation between users and products, from which meaning emerges, instead of on just the relation between function and form (Krippendoff, 2006). Users always begin to decipher product meanings by detecting visual clues before starting to explore a product's function. It is worth knowing what and how users will read or interpret the meaning of products as well as how they feel, especially in the case of products with an intended metaphoric quality. We believe that meaning and emotion are changeable during the operation if we enlarge the time scale. Users might have had different

degrees of experience during each stage of human-product interaction.

Krippendoff (2006, p.170) pointed out that narratives and design are both human creations consisting of cooperative constructions (teller-listeners versus designer-users) and they are emitted for the purpose of being understood. Narratives place artifacts into grammatical constructions that provide the linguistic context of the noun object (Krippendoff, 2006, p.54), and artifacts should be designed so that their interfaces are narratable (Krippendoff, 2006, p.174). He gave an example to show the similarity between the structure of narratives and how we cognize and interact with artifacts: the subject-verb-object constructions are probably responsible for thinking in terms of actor-action-target sequences (Krippendoff, 1990, p.a16). These statements arouse our interest in anatomizing the interaction sequence in the perspective of narrative. Thus, we try to explain the respective roles of product form and action during interaction by borrowing the ideals of narrative sequence, and to explore the emotional potential of semantic interactions by conducting the experiment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

THEORY OF NARRATIVE

Tzvetan Todorov, a structuralist and follower of Roland Barthes' theories, is devoted to the theory of narrative as well as its structure and the ways that these affect readers' perception. He has contributed many important essays on narratology. Todorov (1975) considers that narrative research should be distinguished according to three aspects: the verbal, the syntactical and the semantic. First, the verbal aspect resides in the sentences that constitute the text. Second, by the syntactical aspect, we deal with relations among the parts of the text. Third, the semantic aspect articulates the literary themes in a macro view (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The hierarchy of narrative research adopted from Todorov (1975 & 1977). First of all, it could be divided into three aspects: verbal, syntactical and semantic. The syntactical aspect consists of a four-level hierarchy: predicate, proposition, sequence, and text. The syntactical sequence has different characteristics, according to the type of relation between propositions: temporal, logical and spatial.

Besides revealing the three levels of narrative research, Todorov (1977) further anatomized the following levels of analysis in a hierarchical manner: predicate, proposition, sequence, and text (Figure 1). In this hierarchy, the relations among propositions can be of three types: temporal, logical and spatial. The first is the temporal relation in which events follow one another in an imaginable way and so conventional that its causality is easily ignored. Second, the logical relation (causality) emphasizes that narratives are habitually guided by presuppositions to the particular results. The last is the spatial relation in so far as the statements are juxtaposed due to their similarities (Todorov, 1977). It is easy to confuse the causal relation with the temporal one. The causal narrative also has a temporal attribute; however, people only rarely manage to perceive the latter (Todorov, 1981). According to these theories, we try to infer initially that the temporal relation represents consecutiveness; the logical relation is based on the consequence, and the spatial relation interprets the concept of superimposition.

Furthermore, Todorov dissected the stories of *The Decameron* by way of his grammar hierarchy. In this way, characters could be treated as nouns, their attributes as adjectives and actions as verbs (Hawkes, 2003, p.97). Then, Todorov focused on the context of narrative and argued that an ideal one is composed of five propositions that describe a stable original situation, a perturbing force, disequilibrium, a force in a converse direction, and a reestablished equilibrium (Figure 2). It seems that this five-step construction embodies the recurrent sequence of actor-action-target suggested by Krippendoff. Furthermore, Todorov (1981) stressed the difference between the new equilibrium and the original one. This indicates that the transformations of propositions provide the dynamics of

narrative that could form the very nucleus of the syntactical structure. In the syntactical aspect, stories always begin in peaceful circumstances and end in a similar but actually different situation through characters' actions, followed by the reaction of others. In other words, engrossing storytelling relies on the sophisticated management among propositions under the archetypal syntactical construction, so as to express to listeners a comprehensive theme.

Figure 2. The components of ideal narrative, Todorov, 1981. It implies the construction of subject (n.+adj.)-verb-object (n.+adj.).

INTERACTION PROTOCOL

In the analysis of the ideal interaction sequence, Krippendoff (2006, p.81) expounded that people will describe a product interface as a sequence of actions, followed by the product feedback (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Interaction protocol adopted from Krippendoff (2006). Solid arrows delineate the product mechanism, and dotted lines signify what the user embodies. s_1 represents the first sense or state with which the user responds to product. a_1 is the first user's action oriented by s_1 , serving as input to make product output a feedback state, S_2 , and accomplish the first set of triplets. Subsequently, s_3 is produced by a_2 in the following sequence (the second set of triplets). In brief, $s(n+1)$ is followed by $a(n)$.

In this protocol, users catch product meanings preliminarily according to clues offered by appearance and external conditions, allowing users to trigger the first move of operations. After executing the first action, correctly followed by product feedback, users achieve the first part of the sequence. Meanwhile, products could be treated as being constructed to comply with a collection of triplets: sensing the present

state(s t), acting as the input(a t), and sensing the next state(s (t+1)) (Krippendoff, 2006, p.82). Immediately following this, users could make the recovery through operating in reverse, completing the simplest recurring sequence first. During the second half sequence, users go through the triplets once more. In the aspect of construction, this protocol also embodies the sequence of actor-action-target in which the role of actor is played by the user involved in this protocol. Thus, it is obvious that this protocol would match the hierarchy of ideal narrative consisting of five propositions equal to two sets of triplets (s-a-s in Figure 3).

In addition, to clarify the relation between user's acting and the following product state sensing, Krippendoff explained the role of meaning, as in Figure 3. Neither action nor sense, but rather meaning involves reflection, interpretation or explanation. Meaning connected to the user's action and product state is the crucial factor superior to these two related factors, and represents their imagined possibilities. That is to say, every user's action under a particular external condition is guided by meanings elicited from the product's present state (Krippendoff, 2006, p.82). At any moment of this interaction protocol, the meaning of a product is the range of imaginable actions and senses that the user could anticipate (Krippendoff, 2006, p.83).

THE BASIC SEQUENCES OF INTERACTION

When the concepts of combination among propositions are applied to motion semantics, they take on the following meanings: temporal relation refers to the notion that the meanings which products convey are changeable and dependent on their spontaneous and cyclical transitional appearances; the term "logical relation" refers to user operations according to indexical, iconic and symbolic clues; and the term "spatial relation" refers to the place where the key components are located and can be operated by an atypical action. Then, we find six simplest modes of the interaction sequence induced by examining 85 products, namely: temporal index, regressive logic, reiterative logic, temporal recovery, successive logic, and spatial superimposition. These six simplest modes are the basic building blocks of more complex interactions combining them in the manner of embedding, linking, and alternation. In the early stage of this research, we concentrate on clarifying these simplest elements of

interaction sequence which enable us to discuss the more complex sequence structure in the coming day.

TEMPORAL INDEX

First, temporal index is a mode identical to temporal relation. It embodies the long-lasting and spontaneous change in product appearance. In this mode, users do not need to actually operate the product, but to sense or read the indexical information both from the present appearance and the long-lasting change. After catching enough clues and comparing synthetically, users would try to interpret the product meanings (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The mode of temporal index. The products belonging to this mode express meanings mainly through the present indexical appearance without the user's action ($a_1, a_2, a_3...=0$) at any moment. Furthermore, the user could read and integrate information at a different point of time to catch the meaning.

The timepiece, whether analog or digital, is a usual category of temporal index cases. At any point, people could read the indexical information of a watch via the scale with indexes or the LED numbers on the dial. We just need to see and identify what time it is without any action, and there is no real feedback in temporal index cases. For example, the scale and short hand could be designed to reveal a word when they overlap (see Figure 5). For Decode Clock, as shown at Figure 5, we can recognize a certain number from the hollow of the hour hand, and detect another eleven unreadable codes.

Figure 5. Decode Clock, designed by Arthur Yung and Clement Cheung, produced by ChilliChilly, 2004. People can read different information at a different point of time.

REGRESSIVE LOGIC

Regressive logic states that a user could cause a product to be recovered by operating in reverse, the last half of the sequence. The user's first operation would be guided by the clues in the product's appearance. After reactions and changes in its attributes or appearance, we get its meaning and

confirm its function. When we then want to turn it off, we usually operate it in reverse. Because the orientations of the first and second operations are opposite to each other, this mode is termed regressive logical (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The mode of regressive logic. The main concern here is that the user's first action (a_1) could change the product's attributes in looks (s_2), and then the user could recover its appearance (s_3) by executing the action (a_2) opposite to the original one. The total process could be divided chiefly into two propositions (P_1 vs. P_2).

The concept of regressive logic explains the simplest interaction of most products, the typical example being the toggle switch. However, in trying to be creative, designers usually design an object with a metaphor that might create with a new method of operation and additional meaning. The Criminal Desk Lamp in Figure 7 is a good example. It has an oblique hat-like lampshade "floating" due to the foot-like forked stand. With the hint of the stick attached on the hat, the user would try to touch it and discover that it could be lifted up. Meanwhile, the lamp turns on. When the user wants to turn it off, he or she would retrace the path by instinct to tilt down the hat.

Figure 7. Criminal Desk Lamp, designed by Sebastien Maleville, 2009. User could lift up and then tilt down its hat-like lampshade to turn it on or off.

Actually, its designer wanted to create a lamp to memorialize the king of pop, Michael Jackson, who died in 2009. The unique form represents the famous dancing gestures of Michael Jackson in his song "Smooth Criminal". The inspiration came from Jackson's hat decorated with a black strip, along with Jackson's gestures including closing his feet, inclining his body 45 degrees, and holding the hat. When the lamp is turned on, it recaptures Michael Jackson dancing in the spotlight. In this design, Jackson's dress (form) and gestures (action) are both applied to be interpreted as

a part of the overall meaning. It is possible to anticipate that the user could realize the whole concept after going through the overall sequence. Although the design concept might not be perceived completely at the beginning, the user could still easily accomplish the sequence by tracing its operation back to the lamp's original appearance, and catch the meaning enhanced by the second action.

REITERATIVE LOGIC

Reiterative logic refers to users repeating a motion to control a product. With respect to a building block, this mode is almost equivalent to regressive logic. The similarity is that users also try to operate depending on visual clues. The difference lies in that the second action, the recovering product attribute, is repeating the first action in reiterative logic. For this reason it is termed reiterative logic. In Figure 6, the value of a_2 ($X' = -X$) should be altered as value of a_1 ($X' = X$) in order to illustrate the mode of reiterative logic. In this operating logic, the user could execute the same specific action to fulfill a recurrent loop.

The "Pouring Lamp" (Figure 8) is one example of this. It consists of a "cup" lampshade and a water-flow feature that looks like water spilling out of the cup. Although its form may confuse the user at first glance, the user could identify it as a table lamp. After detecting its details and attributes of appearance, the user might find the switch configured on the top of the lampshade, and then try to touch it to make the lamp turn on. The user may be delighted by the resulting "flow" of light created by flipping the switch, which makes light "spill" like water out of the cup. So far, the action is evident in the form and easy to recognize, and even somewhat humorous. When the user flips the switch once more, the light is turned off. This interaction in the latter half of the sequence somehow implies "water" could be retrieved and put back into the cup. From a semantic point of view, it is possible to confuse the user even though the very first interaction (turning the lamp on) makes sense.

Figure 8. Pouring Lamp, designed by Yeongwoo Kim. This lamp comes with a cup part and a water part. The former is a cup-like lampshade with a power switch; the latter is the base. The concept motive is to emit an emotion-provoking flow of light.

TEMPORAL RECOVERY

Temporal recovery refers to the concept that the artifact will return to its original status independently after use. In the perspective of framework, this mode is similar to regressive logic as well. Nevertheless, the user could leave at any moment after operating the product, and it would be able to recover by itself. In this mode, the second action (a2 in Figure 6) need not be executed anymore. In other words, the value of a2 in the mode of temporal recovery is null.

There is also an example of lamp design, TikTikTik (Figure 9), consisting of an archetypal lampshade and a pull-cord switch resembling a tape measure. This pull cord provides a strong hint of the action, pulling it down, by which the user could turn on the lamp. As the user actually does that, he or she would see the switch becoming elongated without recovering its length at once, and would perceive the light beaming. However, the length of the cord switch is gradually recovered while the light becomes dimmer and dimmer until eventually, it turns off. During this process, whether or not the user pays attention to the long-lasting variation, he or she would finally find its recovery. By operating the lamp several times, he or she would confirm that the length of cord switch refers to the time of recovery.

Figure 9. TikTikTik, produced by BitPlay.

Compared with the triplets of “state - action - next state”, the mode of temporal recovery has a complete set of triplets in the first half, and an incomplete one in the latter half, due to the lack of the second action. Because of this attribute, its second half is similar to the mode of the temporal index. Nevertheless, the arrangement of making automatic recovery reveals the dynamics of the product.

SUCCESSIVE LOGIC

Successive logic refers to how users deal with items requiring more than two causal steps. It is different from other simple modes due to its having at least

three causal propositions. These propositions connect one after another and finally return to the original state. In other words, this simple loop has a longer trajectory in which the user could not recover the original state by carrying out the second operation. This path is illustrated in Figure 10. In Figure 10, a2 (user’s second action) is executed to try to recover, but it appeals to another status leading the user to act in the third proposition and make the product finally return to its original shape.

Figure 10. The mode of successive logic. This sequence of mode consists of more than two complete propositions. Instead of making the product return to the original state (s1), the second action (a2) actually evolves the other reaction in appearance (S3), and opens the following proposition. These added propositions make the total sequence longer, and stop extending it when the original appearance is recovered. Thus, the total process could be divided into at least three propositions (P1, P2 and P3).

The Anna G, corkscrew produced by Alessi, is a famous example belonging to successive logic (Figure 11). Although it looks like a lady wearing a dress, we could easily recognize it as a corkscrew because of its screw and gear bearing (s1). When we begin to put her on the neck of the wine bottle and rotate her head (a1), we would see her arms rising gradually, as if she were dancing (s2). After we push down her arms (a2), the cork is pulled out accompanied with a “pop” (s3). This sound might be interpreted as a burst of applause while she is taking a bow. In the last proposition, we need to pull out the cork from the screw (a3) to restore her original look (s4). This example shows that each subsequent action is executed to remove the reaction caused by the preceding action, and every proposition provides slightly different meanings integrated in the users’ minds.

Figure 11. Anna G, designed by Alessandro Mendini, produced by Alessi, 1994. There are three propositions in the total sequence, and each consequent (a2, and a3) is executed to eliminate the reaction (s2, and s3) caused by the former action (a1, and a2).

SPATIAL SUPERIMPOSITION

Spatial superimposition represents the model of spatial relation mentioned above. The first set of the triplets in this mode is somewhat different from the five other modes. At the beginning, it also guides users to operate via visual clues of icon, index or symbol (Figure 12). However, users will soon learn that the way of operating is not what they expect. After finding out the correct manner, they will discover another sign. Its characteristic lies in that the first and the second images replace each other during interaction. This image-shifting makes users think of their relation. With regard to the latter sequence, the second action is not constrained by any form to accomplish the sequence.

Figure 12. The mode of spatial superimposition. This sequence emphasizes the first set of the triplets. The original state (s1) could supply clues to users. These clues might merely orient users to the available moving part operated actually in an exceptional way (a1). Then, it reveals another product image (s2). The meanings coming from two respective images would be apparently different, and be compared to reveal the designer's concepts. The total sequence is divided into two thematically dependent propositions which could be termed P and Q.

The trick of this mode is to combine two metaphors that share the majority of attributes in the aspects of form or function. Their minor differences become the keys for shifting the meanings. There is an example of a mood lamp, Cupid, which looks like a formula bottle but magnified in size (Figure 13). On the one hand, based on its material and power cord, users could perceive that it should be a lamp. On the other hand, users would associate it with an infant's bottle because of its appearance. They will imagine which part, and which action steps will operate this lamp: shaking the bottle, pressing or sucking the nipple, and spinning off the ring of the bottle. After trying these actions, without obtaining a response, they might discover that the ring can be pulled down vertically, turning the lamp on, and the image shifts from a formula bottle to a condom. This new image will make users compare and establish the connection between two metaphors. Therefore, they would learn that there is causality between them. When users are going through the last half sequence, the second action, pulling up the ring, is

easy to think of and makes sense this time. The latter proposition implies feeding a baby after the sexual behavior or taking off the condom; hence it enforces the completeness of the interaction context.

Figure 13. Cupid, designed by Shih-hung Cheng, 2003. The first set of triplets consists of two dependent images (s1, and s2) and an action (a1) playing the intervening role. Through this action (a1) or the reverse action (a2), Cupid could shift its product images and make users interpret the meaning of this shifting.

EXPERIMENT

After illustrating the six simplest modes of interaction, we try to clarify whether the different degrees of associations in different stages of perceiving visual clues and the user's actions would cause different emotional responses. It is believed that the details of form could be treated as clues that hint at possible movement, and if a form acts in an unexpected way, it will surprise users (Young et al., 2005). In other words, unexpected change could raise the level of surprise. Thus, the experiment is designed to investigate semantic and emotional shifting among all of the interaction steps.

PARTICIPANTS

48 participants (26 females with an average age of 25.6, range 16-38; 22 males with an average age of 27.7, range 22-41) are recruited from the northern area of Taiwan to participate in this study. Among them, 18 participants have professional backgrounds in product design.

STIMULI

The modes mentioned above have common attributes in structure, except for the modes of successive logic comprising more than five steps (or two propositions) and temporal index completely lacking an actual user's involvement. In addition to the four lamps mentioned in the above paragraphs, three others were also chosen as stimuli, and illustrated by five-frame sequences (Figure 14). These five sequential pictures of interaction exhibit the original appearance, user's operation, product feedback, second operation, and product recovery. All seven lamps belong to four simplest modes respectively. Among them, No.2, Smile, is a switch with

a crescent moon-like LED indicator on the bottom. Its decoration with two dots makes it look like a smile when it is turned off, but when turned on, it has an unfriendly facial expression to remind us to save energy. Lamp No.4, Jelly Light, is named for its jelly-like form with a power icon on the top. Users could turn the light on and off by pushing the icon. Lamp No.5, Bang!, could be turned on or off with a gun-shaped remote. The user need only point it at the lamp and pull the trigger. The interaction is as if it was hit with a bullet, and then it revives (turns on) or is killed (turns off).

PROCEDURE

The initial experiment was explained in a formal introduction. Seven interaction sequences were presented in random order. At each step of the sequence, participants were guided to appraise and express their emotion about either form (s1, s2, and s3) or action (a1 and a2) in terms of the surprise and pleasure level (a seven-interval scale) respectively.

RESULTS

Statistical analysis involved multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) followed by the Student-Newman-Keuls (SNK) test for post-hoc multiple comparisons to test all pair-wise differences between means (*p<0.05).

COMPARISON WITHIN THE STEPS OF SINGLE LAMP

All the means and standard deviations at each separate step are shown in Figure 14. The trends of surprise and pleasure at five steps are shown in Figure 15 and Figure 16, respectively.

Figure 15. The line graph of means of surprise at five steps.

No.	Item	Step	1(s1)	2(a1)	3(s2)	4(a2)	5(s3)
1	Criminal Lamp <Regressive logic>						
		Mean : Surprise	4.44 (1.457)	4.63 (1.378)	4.42 (1.499)	3.96 (1.487)	4.10 (1.519)
		(SD) : Pleasure	4.21 (1.597)	4.81 (1.347)	4.56 (1.515)	4.15 (1.557)	4.17 (1.589)
2	Smile <Regressive logic> (Designed by Chou, Mo, Zhou, and Liu, 2010)						
		Mean : Surprise	4.46 (1.129)	4.21 (1.414)	4.60 (1.634)	3.65 (1.564)	4.02 (1.618)
		(SD) : Pleasure	4.81 (1.283)	4.48 (1.288)	4.60 (1.621)	4.25 (1.509)	4.54 (1.611)
3	Pouring Lamp <Reiterative logic>						
		Mean : Surprise	5.06 (1.295)	4.35 (1.523)	5.10 (1.418)	3.90 (1.601)	4.13 (1.453)
		(SD) : Pleasure	5.10 (1.403)	4.52 (1.487)	5.23 (1.433)	4.33 (1.589)	4.13 (1.696)
4	Jelly Light <Reiterative logic> (Produced by Mathmos)						
		Mean : Surprise	4.56 (1.201)	4.17 (1.478)	4.33 (1.629)	3.58 (1.397)	3.67 (1.243)
		(SD) : Pleasure	4.38 (1.671)	4.27 (1.484)	4.19 (1.659)	3.98 (1.313)	3.75 (1.212)
5	Bang! <Reiterative logic> (Produced by BitPlay, 2010)						
		Mean : Surprise	4.96 (1.368)	5.21 (1.458)	4.63 (1.453)	4.83 (1.521)	4.96 (1.271)
		(SD) : Pleasure	4.44 (1.556)	5.15 (1.557)	4.40 (1.660)	5.10 (1.588)	5.04 (1.383)
6	TikTikTik <Temporal recovery>						
		Mean : Surprise	3.25 (1.296)	3.31 (1.355)	3.79 (1.487)	3.94 (1.450)	3.65 (1.376)
		(SD) : Pleasure	3.77 (1.491)	3.85 (1.185)	3.46 (1.529)	3.96 (1.429)	3.92 (1.269)
7	Cupid <Spatial superimposition>						
		Mean : Surprise	4.58 (1.412)	4.94 (1.435)	5.56 (1.583)	4.77 (1.276)	4.81 (1.249)
		(SD) : Pleasure	4.17 (1.534)	4.60 (1.364)	4.60 (1.723)	4.54 (1.166)	4.50 (1.414)

Figure 14. The results of descriptive statistics of all the stimuli. SD is the abbreviation for Standard Deviation. Each picture of the interaction steps is used to detect the emotional effects related to the aspects of surprise and pleasure.

Figure 16. The line graph of means of pleasure at five steps.

Besides descriptive statistics, gender (male and female), background (industrial design, or ID, and not ID), and step (s1, a1, s2, a2, and s3) are set as factors (2X2X5) to detect their influences on the means of each step in every interaction sequence. The brief outcomes of significance tests are shown in Table 1. In factor “Step”, the significance of surprise is easier to emerge than of pleasure (4:1). In “Gender”, it reveals that these 26 female participants tend to appraise higher score both in surprise and pleasure (6:0). And in “Background”, the participants having ID background are easier to express the emotion of surprise than others (3:1).

Factor product	Step	Gender	Background
Criminal	<i>Neither</i>	Pleasure (F>M)	<i>Neither</i>
Smile	surprise	Both (F>M)	Both(ID>Not)
Pouring	Both	Surprise, (F>M)	<i>Neither</i>
Jelly	Surprise	<i>Neither</i>	Both(<i>Not</i> >ID)
Bang!	<i>Neither</i>	Pleasure (F>M)	Surprise (ID>Not)
TikTikTik	<i>Neither</i>	Surprise, (F>M)	Both(ID>Not)
Cupid	Surprise	Surprise, (F>M)	<i>Neither</i>

Table 1. The significant difference of surprise and pleasure in three factors. *p<0.05.

To discuss by single lamp, first of all, there is no significant difference among all the steps of the Criminal Desk Lamp whether in terms of surprise or pleasure. MANOVA also reveals a significant effect of gender on pleasure [female>male, F(1,220)= 4.658, Sig.= 0.032], and interactions between gender and background both on surprise [F(1,220)= 5.472, Sig.= 0.02] and pleasure [F(1,220)= 5.142, Sig.= 0.024]. As to the second lamp, Smile, MANOVA shows gender and background both significantly influence the value of

surprise [female>male, F(1,220)=9.271, Sig.=0.003, and ID>not ID, F(1,220)=6.527, Sig.=0.011, respectively] as well as pleasure [female>male, F(1,220)=6.398, Sig.=0.012, and ID>not ID, F(1,220)=7.406, Sig.=0.007, respectively], and there is an interaction between these two factors in surprise [F(1,220)=7.152, Sig.=0.008]. Significant differences also exist in surprise between step s1 and a2 as well as s2 and a2 (Table 2).

Step	Subset	
	2	1
4(a2)	3.65	
5(s3)	4.02	4.02
2(a1)	4.21	4.21
1(s1)		4.46
3(s2)		4.60

Table 2. The SNK test of Smile’s surprise. *p<0.05.

With regard to the third lamp, the Pouring Lamp, gender significantly influences the level of surprise [female>male, F(1,220)=4.406, Sig.=0.037]. Among the five steps, there are significant differences in surprise ((s2> s1) > (a1> s3> a2), shown in Table 3 (left)) and pleasure ((s2> s1> a1) ≥ (a1> a2> s3), shown in Table 3 (right)). It shows its original look and the feedback state have more significant effects on the two emotional aspects than user actions.

Step	Surprise Subset		Step	Pleasure Subset	
	1	2		2	1
4(a2)	3.90		5(s3)	4.13	
5(s3)	4.13		4(a2)	4.33	
2(a1)	4.35		2(a1)	4.52	4.52
1(s1)		5.06	1(s1)		5.10
3(s2)		5.10	3(s2)		5.23

Table 3. The SNK test of the Pouring Lamp. *p<0.05.

With regard to the result of the fourth lamp, the Jelly Light, a significant effect of background is shown both in surprise [not ID>ID, F(1,220)=13.229, Sig.=0.000] and pleasure [not ID>ID, F(1,220)=10.641, Sig.=0.001]. There are also significant differences in surprise ((s1> s2> a1) ≥ (a1> s3> a2), shown in Table 4). It also shows the first three steps are more able to arouse the user’s curiosity.

Step	Subset	
	2	1
4(a2)	3.58	
5(s3)	3.67	
2(a1)	4.17	4.17
3(s2)		4.33
1(s1)		4.56

Table 4. The SNK test result of the Jelly Light’s surprise. *p<0.05.

The MANOVA result of Lamp No.5, Bang!, displays significant differences of surprise in terms of

background [ID>not ID, $F(1,220)=4.257$, Sig.=0.04], and of pleasure affected by gender [female>male, $F(1,220)=5.468$, Sig.=0.02]. However, there is no significant difference in the two aspects among the five steps.

As for lamp No.6, TikTikTik, MANOVA reveals a significant effect of background both with respect to surprise [ID>not ID, $F(1,220)=4.197$, Sig.=0.042] and pleasure [ID>not ID, $F(1,220)=12.016$, Sig.=0.001]. But among the five steps, there is no significant difference in these two factors.

The statistical result of the last lamp, Cupid, shows a significant effect of gender on surprise [female>male, $F(1,220)=12.404$, Sig.=0.001], as well as of five steps in surprise [$F(4,220)=3.788$, Sig.=0.005]. The SNK test also reveals the significant differences in surprise ($s_2 > (a_1 > s_3 > a_2 > s_1)$), shown in Table 5). It displays that the second image of Cupid, the condom, causes an obvious surprise effect during interaction.

Step	Subset	
	2	1
1(s1)	4.58	
4(a2)	4.77	
5(s3)	4.81	
2(a1)	4.94	
3(s2)		5.56

Table 5. The SNK test of Cupid's surprise. * $p < 0.05$.

COMPARISON OF THE LAMPS

According to the results of the initial analyses mentioned in the above paragraph, we learn the shifting of surprise is much more significant than of pleasure. Therefore, we try to compare the trends of surprise shifting among these lamps. In addition to the original look and the user's first action (s_1 and a_1 in Figure 14), we treat the differences between the user's first action and the original look (a_1-s_1), the feedback in appearance and the original look (s_2-s_1), and two actions (a_2-a_1) as dependent variables. Then, gender, background, and product (7 lamps) are set as factors ($2 \times 2 \times 7$) to detect their influences on five foregoing variables by MANOVA, followed by the SNK test. We propose three hypotheses. First, the original look and the user's first action (s_1 and a_1) might be restricted respectively by the specific form and action. Second, the shifting from s_1 to a_1 displays the potential of visual clues. Third, two other variables (s_2-s_1 , a_2-a_1) might reveal the characteristic of four interaction modes because the variables of difference could be used to compare different products as if they were

sharing the same base without being influenced by the types of form or action.

The result shows there is no main effect of gender and background, but all five variables are significantly different among the lamps. First of all, with respect to the original form (s_1), the surprise of TikTikTik is significantly different from the others (Table 6).

Lamp	Subset	
	2	1
TikTikTik	3.25	
Criminal		4.44
Smile		4.46
Jelly		4.56
Cupid		4.58
Bang!		4.96
Pouring		5.06

Table 6. The SNK test of surprise by s_1 . * $p < 0.05$.

TikTikTik is the only lamp among the seven that looks like an archetypal lamp; thus it is less attractive in appearance. Second, the result of the SNK test also shows that the user's first action of TikTikTik evokes significantly less surprise than the others do (Table 7). It suggests that it provides such a significant and obvious clue as to how to operate it that users would think its operational action dull. The highest subset consists of Bang!, Cupid and Criminal of which the first action (to trigger, to pull down the ring, and to lift up the hat) is either unusual or hard to discover.

Lamp	Subset		
	2	3	1
TikTikTik	3.31		
Jelly		4.17	
Smile		4.21	
Pouring		4.35	
Criminal		4.63	4.63
Cupid			4.94
Bang!			5.21

Table 7. The SNK test of surprise by a_1 . * $p < 0.05$.

Third, Cupid, Bang! and Criminal also have the more obvious positive shifting from step s_1 to a_1 (Table 8). It suggests that the operation methods of these three lamps could be hooks in the sequences.

Lamp	Subset	
	2	1
Pouring	-0.71	
Jelly	-0.40	-0.40
Smile	-0.25	-0.25
TikTikTik		0.06
Criminal		0.19
Bang!		0.25
Cupid		0.35

Table 8. The SNK test of surprise from s_1 to a_1 . * $p < 0.05$.

Fourth, Cupid has the most significant positive variance from step s1 to s2 (Table 9). It implies that the divergent image at step s2 will arouse users' curiosity. We infer that the more obvious difference between s1 and s2 of TikTikTik is caused by its significantly low s1 value, not by its s2.

Lamp	Subset	
	2	1
Bang!	-0.33	
Jelly	-0.23	
Smile	-0.02	
Pouring	0.04	
Criminal	0.15	
TikTikTik	0.54	0.54
Cupid		0.98

Table 9. The SNK test of surprise from s1 to s2. *p<0.05.

Lastly, after testing all the variances between two operations among the seven lamps, we propose that TikiTikTik is the only lamp showing positive and significant differences from a1 to a2 (Table 10). We initially infer that the mode of temporal recovery might continually arouse the user's curiosity at step a2 because this mode lacks any need for the user's actual second action and displays its spontaneous movement.

Lamp	Subset	
	2	1
Criminal	-0.67	
Jelly	-0.58	
Smile	-0.56	
Pouring	-0.46	
Bang!	-0.38	
Cupid	-0.17	
TikTikTik		0.63

Table 10. The SNK test of surprise from a1 to a2. *p<0.05.

CONCLUSIONS

After this early-stage investigation, it shows that the semantic shifting actually can affect the elicitation of emotion, and an atypical form and an operational action will give rise to user's surprise at the each step of interaction. As to this point, Scherer (1988) stated that most emotions are response to a change in the stimulation either via real external situations or internal mental events such as the recall of memory that might alter user's thought. Thus, emotions elicited by the shifting in the interaction protocol would involve the aspects both of external situations (e.g. action, sense) and internal mental events (meaning). However, in the above investigation, we focus on detecting the impact of user's actions and product appearances on emotion. The change of meaning is not

set as a key factor yet to clarify the relation between meaning and emotion. Furthermore, the stimuli in this study are sequential pictures shown by five frames. The lack of the participant's direct contact with the products might cause significant biases. This is the inevitable drawback inherent in the experiment design. Hence, we will carry out further experiments in the future to test real-interaction devices and explore the emotional effect of form, action, and meaning.

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